

ISic4395

I.Sicily inscription 4395

Language

Sikel

Type

unknown

Material

volcanic (lava stone)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Seen by Campagna 2005

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

Not recorded, but assumed to be local

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del Teatro Antico

Physical Description

fragmentary block, broken into three joining pieces and damaged on at least three sides (above, to right and below)

Dimensions

Height 21 cm

Width 56 cm

Depth 11 cm

Layout

parts of two lines of letters running left to right obliquely across the face

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Deeply incised crude letters of Greek form. P is open, E has straight horizontal bars, A is broad with an approximately straight bar.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 60-65 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. δια ξο[---]

2. ρειαιενι[---]

Apparatus

Text from Manganaro 1965

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

Bibliography

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Cordano, F. 2012. Iscrizioni monumentali dei Siculi. *Aristonothos*. 4: 165-184. At 169

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Photo L. Campagna 2005-03-31